

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF FISHERIES IN THE KYRGYZ REPUBLIC IN MODERN CONDITIONS: CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

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ABSTRACT

The article examines the current state of fisheries in the Kyrgyz Republic and analyzes the key challenges and opportunities facing this industry. The study used data on production indicators, export and import of fish products, as well as environmental aspects of fish farming. Particular attention is paid to the impact of climate change, environmental problems and economic factors affecting the development of fisheries. Based on the analysis, recommendations were proposed to improve the management of fisheries resources and increase their sustainability in a changing environment.

Keywords: fisheries, aquaculture.

Purpose of the study:

Conduct an analysis of fisheries in the Kyrgyz Republic in modern conditions to identify challenges and opportunities in this sector.

Research objectives:

1. Assess the current state of fisheries: Analyze the existing structures, processes and results of fisheries in the country.
2. Identify key challenges: Identify the problems and difficulties faced by fisheries, including environmental, economic and technical aspects.
3. Analyze opportunities: Explore potential opportunities for fisheries development, including the introduction of new technologies, improved resource management and expanded markets.
4. Assess the influence of environmental and economic factors: Investigate how changes in environmental and economic conditions affect fisheries and their productivity.
5. Develop recommendations: Based on the analysis, offer recommendations for improving the condition of fisheries, increasing their efficiency and sustainability.
6. Determine staffing needs: Assess the need to train qualified specialists in the field of fish production and propose measures for training and advanced training of personnel

Materials and methods.

To analyze fisheries in the Kyrgyz Republic in modern conditions, the following materials and methods can be used:

- statistical data, Official reports and statistics from government agencies, scientific research and publications.
- data analysis, comparative analysis.

SWOT-анализ:

- Assess the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of fisheries in the Kyrgyz Republic.
- Field research:

- Conducting surveys and interviews with fish farm owners and workers.
- Monitoring and assessing the condition of fisheries facilities on site.
- Analysis of the environmental situation:
- Assess the condition of water bodies and ecosystems in which fishing is carried out in order to identify environmental risks and problems.

Results and discussion.

Fisheries and aquaculture play an important role in the economy and food security of the Kyrgyz Republic. In the context of a changing climate, socio-economic changes and growing demand for fish as a source of protein, analyzing the current state of fisheries in Kyrgyzstan, as well as identifying the challenges and opportunities facing the industry, is an urgent task.

The fishing industry in the Kyrgyz Republic has never played a major role due to the lack of opportunities for its development. The fish was produced only fresh and sluggish, since the volume of fishing did not allow the organization of round-the-clock production of other types of products. For example, for the continuous operation of small shops, such as the smoking shop at the Grigorievsky fish processing plant, sea fish was imported.

The history of fishing on Lake Issyk-Kul begins at the end of the 19th century (Berg, 1930), when from 174 to 1048 quintals of fish were caught per year. Until 1930 (according to Lindberg, 1935), the fish catch did not exceed 1000 centners per year.

However, with the creation of the Issyk-Kul fish processing plant in 1931, fish catches in Issyk-Kul began to grow and by the 1960s reached 11-12 thousand centners per year, of which 90% were chebachek (*Leuciscus bergi*), a mass-produced low-value fish. [1]

According to the Law of the Kyrgyz Republic "On Aquaculture, Fisheries and Protection of Aquatic Biological Resources" dated March 17, 2021, a state fish-

ery register is maintained for the purpose of state accounting in the field of fisheries. The procedure for forming and maintaining the register is approved by the Government of the Kyrgyz Republic and the authorized state fisheries management body - the Department of Pastures, Livestock and Fisheries of the Ministry of Agriculture, Food Industry and Land Reclamation of the Kyrgyz Republic.

The register contains information:

1. About fisheries entities.
2. About fishery reservoirs used for the purposes of aquaculture, fish farming or fishing.
3. On the quantity of commercial fish caught and grown and fish farm products.
4. About commercial fish and fish-breeding products imported into the territory of the Kyrgyz Republic or exported beyond its borders.

The register is posted on the official website of the authorized body in the field of fisheries and is an open and accessible source of information. [2,4]

However, there are also those who are not included in the state register. These are, for example, those who built a fish farm in their yard and did not register it anywhere, or rented plots in forest and pasture areas and opened fish pools there. The Fishing Industry Association of the Kyrgyz Republic estimates that such illegal fish farms have an impact on the export of products.

Fishing entities, regardless of their form of ownership, are required to keep records and provide the authorized body with information:

1. On the volumes of commercial fish and fish farming products grown, caught and sold.
2. On the volume of juvenile fish released into water bodies for the purpose of stocking water bodies with fish. [2]

Fishery reservoirs of national importance include natural and artificial reservoirs (lakes, reservoirs, rivers and their sections), which:

1. Are used or can be used for fishing activities.
2. They are important for the reproduction of fish stocks. /

Such reservoirs include lakes Issyk-Kul, Son-Kul and Toktogul, Bazar-Korgon, Kirov, Orto-Tokoy reservoirs. Lake Issyk-Kul is a fishery reservoir of national importance with the zoning of the biosphere territory "Issyk-Kol" into separate zones (core zone, buffer zone, transition zone, remediation zone) with a special regime of protection and use. [2]

To date, more than 2,700 reservoirs suitable for growing fish are being studied in Kyrgyzstan. Of these, 274 registered fish farms have started official operations. It is noteworthy that 73% of these farms are located in the Chui region. According to the law, all public water bodies are water bodies of state importance,

and the main user of fishery water bodies is the Ministry of Agriculture and Water Resources of the Republic represented by the Department of Fisheries.

In the Issyk-Kul region, 11 fishery entities are registered, of which only the Tonsky Branch fish farm (Bokonbaevo village) is state-owned and financed by the budget. The rest have been privatized, transformed into LLCs or private enterprises. All fishing entities are located on the territory of the Issyk-Kul and Ton regions and in the city of Karakol. There are currently no fisheries activities (except for poaching) in the Ortotokoy Reservoir.

In the Issyk-Kul region, reservoirs are divided into natural and natural, which, in addition, are divided into fishing and general reservoirs.

The Law "On Fisheries", adopted by the Legislative Assembly of the Jogorku Kenesh of the Kyrgyz Republic on June 13, 1997, includes Lake Issyk-Kul and the Ortotokoy Reservoir as fishery reservoirs in the region, while others are public water bodies. The reservoirs of the region are home to 35-37 species of fish. The only commercial fish of Lake Issyk-Kul are: carp, carp, marinka, osman, bream, trout, whitefish, pike perch, chebak and chebak (out of 28 species registered to date). [2]

Pond fishing in the Kyrgyz Republic is the main and most productive area of modern aquaculture. Today, the area of the pond water fund is about 1020 hectares, including 825 hectares intended for feeding, 195 hectares for cultivation.

This form of fishing is based on multicultural approaches, including the farming of rainbow trout, carp and plant fish species. The main fish farming facilities are the Issyk-Kul, Chui and Osh regions, where together more than 75 species of fish are produced in the country.

Garden fish farming is a promising area of the fishing industry in the Kyrgyz Republic, which has high economic efficiency.

The best conditions for its development are Lake Issyk Kul, reservoirs of the Naryn Cascade of the hydroelectric power station, as well as other water bodies. [3]

In the nine months of 2023, 2,994 tons of fish products were exported from the Kyrgyz Republic, which is much more than 2,000 tons in the same period of the previous year. In 2022, 9 companies decided to deliver; in 2023, 5 companies unloaded 3 thousand tons of cargo.

This confirms the development of exports, which continue under strict compliance with veterinary and sanitary requirements, as well as regulations on fish products.[5]

In 2019, 33,398 fishing cards and tickets were issued for a total amount of 1,057,989 soms. (Table 1) [5]

Table 1

Information on tickets and cards issued for 9 months of 2019 in the Kyrgyz Republic

№	Name of fish	Number of issued fish cards and tickets (pcs)	Amount (som)	note
1	For river trout	22625	884625-00	
2	On the river toman	380	90060-00	
3	For large fish (pike, pike perch, catfish, carp)	100	28700-00	
4	into small pieces (crucian carp, sabrefish).	293	54604-00	
	total	33398	1 057 989	

[6]

The reduction in average annual fish catches in Lake Issyk-Kul since the 70s was mainly due to a decrease in the number of chebak and the almost complete loss of carp, marinka, and naked osman from the fishery. Experts consider the following factors to be the reasons for the decline in the numbers of chebak and catches in general:

fishing for chebak and other fish during the spawning period by-catch of immature juveniles.

- increase in the number of predators.
- disproportionate load on fishing areas.
- prohibited fishing gear.
- poaching, recreational fishing

In the Issyk-Kul region, partly in the Naryn region, there is a reservoir of the Orto Tokoy type, with an area of 23.20 hectares at the oil refinery, the depth of the dam is 40 meters. Experts believe that the water is suitable for stocking trout and whitefish, the choice of which depends on the characteristics of the fishery.

At one time, it produced producers of naked Ottomans, carp and Issyk-Kul trout. The original predators - marinkas, Tien Shan loaches, minnows, river forms of naked osmans - have little value in fishing, but can serve as a food source for large fish.

The reservoir can be used as a reservoir for feeding fish farming, and for cage rearing of juveniles and commercial fish. [1.5]

For the artificial reproduction of commercial fish on the southern shore of Lake Issyk-Kul, the Ton fish hatchery was launched in 1964, and then the Karakol one. They specialize in artificial breeding of trout, osman and whitefish, since the natural reproduction of these species, especially salmon and whitefish, is complicated by the conditions of spawning and rearing of juveniles.

The production capacity of these factories was quite large. From 1965 to 1985, 99.3 million units were obtained from them. trout larvae, 142.0 million pieces. whitefish larvae and 67.5 million pieces. naked ottoman fry. In recent years, the productivity of factories has decreased; in 1997, only 500 thousand trout larvae were obtained at the Ton fish hatchery. The Karakol plant is practically destroyed; there is no fish farming going on there.

However, if we do not continue work on the artificial reproduction of valuable commercial fish - trout, whitefish, peled, naked osman - then their numbers in the lake will gradually lose their commercial importance. Scientists have paid sufficient attention to the

artificial breeding of Issykul fish. There are detailed instructions for breeding trout, whitefish, and osman. [1.5]

Fish farming standards for biotechnical methods of reproduction and cultivation of different types of fish largely depend on the temperature regime of the environment.

To clarify the zonal division of commercial fish farms in the Kyrgyz Republic, natural climate factors in one or another territory of commercial fish farms are indicated: duration of the growing season, predominant soil types, productivity indicators of reservoirs that are sources of water supply. [6]

The Orto-Tokoy reservoir in the Issyk-Kul region (partly in the Naryn region) has an area of 2320 hectares and a depth of 40 m at the dam. Experts believe that it is suitable for breeding trout and whitefish. Naked Osman, carp and Issyk-Kul trout have already been released into it. The ichthyofauna is of little commercial value, but can be a food source for large fish. The reservoir is suitable for feeding fish farming and cage farming.

Fish farming and biological standards depend on temperature conditions. The zonal division of fish farms in the Kyrgyz Republic is determined by natural and climatic factors. Planting material is obtained at Boru-Bashsky, Karakolsky and Tonsky fish breeding enterprises. The lakes of the Issyk-Kul basin are classified as whitefish and whitefish-trout. The profitability of fish farming is achieved by growing polycultures and using scientific advances.

Fishing in rivers is amateur in nature. The rivers of the Issykul region are used for raising juvenile trout and osman, as well as for spawning trout, marinka and osman. The lake's tributaries can support up to 4 million juveniles. [1]

The lack of qualified specialists in the field of fish production leads to ineffective solutions to problems related to fish treatment, its cultivation and other aspects. This creates risks for the food safety of fish produced in the regions of the Kyrgyz Republic. Therefore, it is important to pay attention to the need to train qualified personnel and organize training in this area to improve the efficiency and safety of fisheries.

SWOT analysis of fisheries in the Kyrgyz Republic

Strengths:

1. Availability of natural resources: The Kyrgyz Republic has several large reservoirs, such as Lake Issyk-Kul, Toktogul, Orto-Tokoy reservoirs and others, which can be used for fish farming.

2. Legislative framework: The adoption of the law “On Aquaculture, Fisheries and the Protection of Aquatic Biological Resources” and the creation of a state fisheries register help to systematize and control fisheries.

3. Developing exports: In 2023, exports of fish products increased significantly, which indicates an increase in demand for Kyrgyz fish products and compliance with veterinary and sanitary requirements.

4. Pond fish farming: This area is the main and productive one in Kyrgyzstan, with a high share of production in the Issyk-Kul, Chui and Osh regions.

Weaknesses:

1. Lack of qualified professionals: The lack of professionals in fisheries and aquaculture makes it difficult to effectively manage fisheries and can threaten product safety.

2. Inefficiency of existing fish factories: Reduced productivity in old fish factories, such as Karakol, and the need to update infrastructure.

3. Illegal activities: The presence of informal fisheries that are not included in the government register and the problem of poaching, which affects the export of products and fish stocks.

Opportunities:

1. Development of cage fish farming: This area has high potential, especially on Lake Issyk-Kul and other reservoirs with favorable conditions.

2. Integration with agriculture: Development of polyculture and integration of fisheries with agricultural production can improve efficiency and profitability.

3. Research and Innovation: Possibility of improving biotechnology and fish farming methods, which can increase productivity and improve product quality.

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Threats:

1. Decline in fish stocks: Decline in the numbers of chebak, carp and other commercial species due to overfishing and environmental problems.

2. Export restrictions: The introduction of restrictions on the export of fishery products, especially in Russia, may have a negative impact on fisheries in Kyrgyzstan.

3. Environmental and climate changes: Changes in climate and ecology can affect the productivity of water bodies and conditions for fish farming.

Recommendations:

1. Professional development of specialists: Investment in education and training in the field of fisheries.

2. Infrastructure modernization: Upgrading and modernizing fish hatcheries and equipment.

3. Control and monitoring: Tightening control over illegal activities and poaching.

4. Invest in Research: Support research to improve fish farming methods and productivity.

1. Conclusions and offers

Conclusions:

1. Historical development and current status: The fishing industry of the Kyrgyz Republic has a long history, but its development is limited due to insufficient catch volumes and lack of infrastructure. In recent decades, fish catches in Lake Issyk-Kul have declined significantly due to various environmental and management problems.

2. Legislation and regulation: The adoption of the law “On Aquaculture, Fisheries and the Protection of Aquatic Biological Resources” and the creation of a state fishery register contributed to the regulation and control in this area. However, there are problems with informal, unlisted fisheries and poaching.

3. Current situation in the fishing industry: Pond fish farming is the main and most productive area in the Kyrgyz Republic. Cage fish farming has prospects for further development, however, restrictions on the cultivation of rainbow trout and introduced predatory fish species in Lake Issyk-Kul have led to a reduction in production.

3. Export: In 2023, there is a significant increase in the export of fish products, which indicates the development and increase in demand for the product. However, export restrictions, especially in Russia, could negatively impact the industry.

4. Environmental and climate change: The decline in the number of commercial fish species is associated with overfishing, environmental problems and climate change.

Offers:

1. Professional development: It is important to invest in fisheries education and training to improve production efficiency and ensure product safety.

2. Modernization of infrastructure: Modernization and updating of existing fish hatcheries and equipment is necessary to improve productivity and product quality.

3. Strengthen controls and monitoring: There is a need to strengthen controls on illegal activities, poaching and informal fisheries to preserve fish stocks and improve export performance.

4. Invest in Research: Supporting research and introducing innovative fish farming methods will help increase productivity and improve the quality of fish products.

5. Development of cage fish farming: Continued development of cage fish farming, especially on Lake Issyk-Kul and other suitable water bodies, can contribute to increased production and increased profits.

6. Integration with agriculture: Development of polyculture and integration of fisheries with agricultural production can improve the efficiency and sustainability of the industry.

7. Protection and restoration of ecosystems: Taking measures to protect fish migration routes, habitats and spawning grounds will help preserve and restore fish stocks, as well as maintain the ecosystem of water bodies.

References

1. FISHERIES [Electronic resource] - Access mode: <https://rus.gateway.kg/analiticheskie-materialy/biosfernaya-territoriya-ysyk-kyol-1998/> (access date 07/17/2024). [Published in English]

2. LAW OF THE KYRGYZ REPUBLIC dated March 17, 2021 No. 35 On aquaculture, fisheries and protection of aquatic biological resources [Electronic resource] Access mode: https://base.spin-form.ru/show_doc.fwx?rgn=131324 [Published in Russian]

3. Resolution of the Government of the Kyrgyz Republic dated October 15, 2019 Action plan for the implementation of the Fisheries and Aquaculture Development Program in the Kyrgyz Republic for 2019-2023 /ru [Electronic resource] - Access mode <https://cbd.minjust.gov.kg> > edition [Published in Russian]

4. Unified State Fisheries Register of the Kyrgyz Republic. [Electronic resource] - Access mode: https://agro.gov.kg/bfd_download (accessed 07/17/2024). [Published in English]

5. Protection of fish stocks [Electronic resource] - Access mode: https://agro.gov.kg/bfd_download (access date 07/17/2024). [Published in English]

6. Order of the Ministry of Agriculture [Electronic resource] - Access mode: farms, <https://cbd.minjust.gov.kg/200324/edition/929270/ru/22.07.2024> [Published in Russian]